

IMPACT OF COMPOSITE CYLINDERS

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ABSTRACT

Transverse impact of composite structures is of interest because of the possibility of accidental damage. The present paper presents experiments and analysis on impact of fiber composite cylinders, with the primary goal of developing techniques for extrapolation of results from laboratory scale to full scale structures. The experimental results show that structural response can be accurately scaled. Agreement between measured strains and a closed-form analysis is good, and the analysis can thus be used to investigate the details of the mechanical response in the cylinders.

KEYWORDS: Composites; impact; dynamic response; scaling rules.

1. INTRODUCTION

The effects of transverse impact in fiber composite structures is of much interest. Fiber composites are known to be susceptible to damage from accidental transverse impacts, and it is hoped that a knowledge of the mechanics of the impact will lead to improved designs. The present paper discusses impact in fiber composite cylinders, and considers both dynamic and quasi-static impact conditions.

There is an extensive literature on the effects of impact in fiber composites. Much of the work has been conducted on flat plates, and has been concerned with observing the amount and nature of the damage that occurs from impact [1-5]. This work has been valuable in establishing the type of damage that could occur, and the effects of substitution of materials, such as higher toughness matrices, for example.

A major drawback of present methods is that no methodology exists for extrapolating from laboratory tests to the composite structures of interest. A major goal of the present program is to attempt to understand the mechanics of the impact event in sufficient detail so that predictions could be made on full scale structures with confidence. Because of the complexity of the formation of damage in composites, it was concluded that laboratory tests of some type were essential, and that methods of scaling from subscale specimens to larger structures were an important component of the methodology. Accordingly, emphasis was placed on understanding scaling in impact.

The overall program on damage involved an extensive set of impact experiments on composite plates and cylinders. The tests were carried out under conditions that were believed to be both quasi-static and dynamic, using a pendulum drop-weight apparatus and an airgun, respectively, to carry out these tests. The experimental program involved tests on specimens of different size, that were constructed to verify and/or determine appropriate rules for scaling and size effects. A total of five sizes of plates were used, varying in size by a factor of 5. Two sizes of cylinders were used, that varied by a factor of 3.30.

The results of the impact experiments on plates have been presented previously in [6,7], and some aspects of the cylinder experiments have been given in [8]. The purpose of the present paper is to give an overview of the cylinder experiments and analysis procedures, and present new results from the analysis.

2. EXPERIMENTAL

The cylinders used were made of IM7/55A carbon/epoxy, filament wound by Hercules Aerospace. The specifications of the sizes and layups are given in Table 1. Two sizes of cylinders were used that had inside diameters of 96.5 mm and 319 mm, respectively. The design of the cylinders was intended to verify scaling rules for structural response that had been developed by Christoforou [9]. To achieve geometric scaling, the cylinder diameter, length, ply group thickness, and dimensions of the impactor were all varied by a scale factor equal to 3.30.

The experimental apparatus for the dynamic experiments utilized compressed air to drive a cylindrical impactor along a barrel, permitting close control of impact velocity and impact site. The specimens were instrumented with strain gages placed adjacent to the impact site on the outside of the cylinder. Data were recorded with a high-speed computer controlled data acquisition system. The cylinders were supported with rings to simulate simply-supported boundary conditions used in the analysis. More detail on the apparatus can be found in [6].

Velocities for the dynamic impact experiments were based on the results of previous plate experiments, and were established so that the maximum velocity produced extensive damage and possible partial penetration of the cylinder. Three lower velocities were also used that had nominal levels of 20%, 30%, and 55% of this value. The lowest velocity was used to study linear response without damage effects. The cylindrical projectiles had hemispherical tip diameters that were 1, 1/2, and 1/4 of the projectile diameter.

3. ANALYSIS

An analysis of the cylinders under conditions of dynamic impact has been developed, and was used extensively in understanding the present experiments [10]. The analysis assumes rigid projectile impact of an orthotropic cylinder that is simply supported at the ends. The procedure is based on Fourier series expansions of the cylinder equilibrium equations, coupled with Laplace transform techniques to solve the dynamics problem. An important limitation of the solution is that it assumes a linearized Hertz contact zone stiffness, while a nonlinear contact zone stiffness is believed to more accurately describe the very local deformations at the impact site [11,12]. However it has been shown in numerical comparisons for composite plates that for relatively flexible structures, the use of a linearized contact stiffness can give reasonable accuracy [13].

As described in detail by Christoforou and Swanson [10], the analysis is based on a Fourier series expansion of the equations of motion presented by Birman and Bert [14]. The constitutive equations for a specially orthotropic material ($B_{ij}=0$, $A_{16}=A_{26}=D_{16}=D_{26}=0$) have been used to relate the stress, moment, and shear resultants to the midsurface strains ϵ_i^0 , curvatures κ_i , and average transverse shear strains γ_{xz} and γ_{yz} . These equations are solved by assuming separable functions in time and Fourier series functions in space. The impact load is also expanded in a Fourier series. Birman and Bert [14] obtained equations similar to those that result from these operations, and showed that they can be reduced to a single linear second-order differential equation for each Fourier series component. The solution to the time dependent impact problem is then obtained by Laplace transform techniques, using rigid body dynamics for the projectile. The Laplace transforms can be evaluated by simple residue theory, giving finally an expression for the Fourier series components of the deflection. More detail on the development of the above is given in [10]. From the above, the deflection and strain histories at any point of the shell can be evaluated. The equations have been coded into a computer program which was employed for the present study. The material properties used in the analysis are given in Table 2.

4. SCALING RULES

Extrapolation of results from subscale experiments is a key issue in understanding the response of composite structures to impact loads. As discussed above, previous work on scaling has been accomplished by Morton [15], Jackson [16], and Qian and Swanson [6] on scaling of results for dynamic loading of plates. The results developed by Christoforou [9] for scaling in tests of cylinders are quite similar to those used on plates in [7], and imply the following. The scaling analysis shows that the strain levels developed during impact should be the same if the radius, thickness, and length of the cylinders are scaled geometrically. That is, if the scale factor is termed λ , then all of the dimensions should be scaled by λ . Note that this requires the ply group thicknesses in the lamination layup to also be scaled. Further, the impactor dimensions should be scaled by the same scale factor, so that impact mass varies as λ^3 . The impact velocity should be held constant.

5. RESULTS

An illustration of the scaling of the results between the two sizes of cylinders is given in Fig 1. A consequence of the scaling described above, is that the time duration of the impact should vary linearly with the scale factor. The results shown in Fig 1 illustrate that the strain histories between tests on the two sizes of cylinders can be superposed with a high degree of accuracy if the time scale is divided by the scale factor. This result is characteristic of all of the cylinder test results and was also observed previously in the dynamic plate experiments [7], where five different plate sizes were used. This result is believed to verify the accuracy of scaling of the linear response of the structure.

Comparisons of the predicted and measured strain response are shown in Fig 2. It can be seen that the comparison is quite good, indicating that the basic features of the structural response at low impact velocities are represented in the dynamic analysis.

As mentioned previously, tests were also carried out using a heavier impact mass and a pendulum apparatus. The impact masses used for the smaller cylinders were 2.86 gm for the airgun experiments and 183 gm for the pendulum experiments. One of the unknown factors in impact is how the structural response, and the damage, vary over changes in impact mass and velocity. One rule that is often followed is to assume that impact energy should be held constant when comparing impacts at different conditions. However the basis for this rule has not been established. It is interesting to compare the calculated response between the 2.86 gm and the 183 gm impacts. The calculated forces are shown in Fig 3, and illustrate the large difference in the time scales. Interestingly, the magnitude of the impact force is seen to be quite similar. In this figure and those to follow, the impact energy has been held constant. A comparison of the calculated radial displacement at the point of impact is shown in Fig 4. This comparison illustrates the

importance of dynamic effects in the analysis, as the calculated displacements are quite different even though the calculated forces are similar. Another comparison is shown in Fig 5, where the calculated surface strains along the inner surface of the cylinder at the time of peak strain are compared, at the location $\theta=0$. The strains in this figure are plotted as a function of the distance from the impact point. The strains in the light mass (dynamic) impact are seen to decay more rapidly with distance from the impact point than in the heavy mass impact. However the striking feature of this comparison is the similarity of the strain response. The difference between the peak values is seen to be on the order of ten percent.

6. DISCUSSION

As pointed out above, the complications of impact loading suggest that a combination of analysis and laboratory tests will be required to predict the effects of impact in structures of interest. The results shown here indicate that scaling of the structural response can be effectively predicted. Previous results on plates [7] over an even wider range of sizes also support this view. The scaling results combined with the analysis also suggest other procedures for designing suitable laboratory tests for extrapolation to full scale structures. For example, it has proved possible to use the laboratory plate tests to estimate impact parameters in cylinders, and thus presumably to more complicated structures. This requires selection of the appropriate sizes and boundary conditions in the plates to simulate the applied load levels and spatial gradients of these levels.

Scaling of damage formation is a more complicated matter, however. Previous work on plates indicates that delamination shows a dependence on the square root of absolute size characteristic of fracture mechanics [7]. The preliminary results of the present investigation on cylinders suggests that this is also the case here. On the other hand, sectioning work suggests that this type of size effect in producing fiber damage is much less pronounced and may be absent. Further work on the damage modeling will be reported elsewhere.

The close agreement of the analysis with experiment is highly encouraging. The closed form linear analysis is a convenient tool for investigation of the details of the stress and strain fields, but is obviously a simplification of the inherent nonlinearities of the impact event. One nonlinearity is that of the contact zone stiffness. However a comparison of solution techniques applied to impact of plates indicates that there is a wide range of conditions over which the nonlinearity of the contact stiffness does not have an appreciable effect on the calculated response [13]. Another area of concern is that of the applicability of shell equations in modeling the response near the contact zone. Again in previous work on plates, good agreement between the analysis and experiment was found for strains behind the

impact point [6]. It appears that both in the previous work on plates and in the present experiments, that the technique of applying the loading over a finite sized contact zone, rather than just using a point load approximation, gives improved accuracy in the calculations near the impact site.

The calculations and experiments performed to compare the effects of impact mass and velocity are quite interesting. Although not shown, the results indicate that the pendulum impacts can be classified as quasi-static, in that inertia effects within the cylinder had a negligible effect on the results. The analysis of the airgun impacts, on the other hand, indicates that these tests were strongly influenced by inertia effects and are thus dynamic in nature. In spite of these differences, the analysis predicted strain levels that were within about 10% for the quasi-static and dynamic events, if the applied impact energy levels were constant. This idea has been used intuitively by many investigators, but the results shown here give additional support to this procedure. The analysis results are also supported by the experiments, both with respect to strain levels observed and the degree of damage induced.

7. SUMMARY AND CONCLUSIONS

Impact experiments have been carried out on composite cylinders in an attempt to develop rules for extrapolation of results from laboratory scale to full scale structures. Measurements of surface strains on two cylinders that varied in size by a factor of 3.3 show that the structural response can be accurately scaled. Good agreement was achieved between the experiments and a dynamic closed-form analysis based on Fourier series expansions and Laplace transform techniques. An interesting result of the analysis is that the procedure of holding impact energy constant is found to produce similar strain levels in the cylinders over a range of quasi-static to dynamic impacts.

8. REFERENCES

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Table 1. Cylinder and impactor configurations

parameter	small cylinder	large cylinder
material	IM7/55A	IM7/55A
inside dia., mm	96.5	319
wall thickness, mm	1.63	5.08
cylinder length, m	0.559	1.89
length between supports, m	0.184	0.610
projectile mass, g	2.85	102
projectile dia. (D), mm	6.35	20.57
projectile tip dia	D, D/2, D/4	D, D/4
Layup 1	[±18/90 ₂] _s	[±18 ₂ /±18 ₂ /90 ₈] _s
Layup 2	---	[±18 ₂ /90 ₈ /±18 ₂] _s

Table 2. Material properties of IM7/55A carbon/epoxy used in the analysis.

Longitudinal Modulus, E ₁₁	148 GPa (21.6 Msi)
Transverse Modulus, E ₂₂	7.58 GPa (1.10 Msi)
In Plane Shear Modulus, G ₁₂	3.57 GPa (0.518 Msi)
Transverse Shear Modulus, G ₂₃	2.62 GPa (0.380 Msi)
Poissons Ratio, ν ₁₂	0.266
Poissons Ratio, ν ₂₃	0.311

Fig 1. Scaling of strain gage response in dynamic impact of ID=96.3 mm ($\lambda=1$) and ID=319 mm ($\lambda=3.3$) composite cylinders.

Fig 2. Comparison of experimental and analytical solution for hoop direction strain gage response in dynamic impact of ID=319 mm cylinder with layup 2. Impact velocity= 6.77 m/s; strain gage located at $x=0$, $\theta=1.91^\circ$ from impact site.

Fig 3. Calculation of impact force in 2.86 gm and 183 gm impact of 96.5 mm ID cylinder. Impact energy = 0.213 J.

Fig 4. Calculation of displacement/R at impact site in 2.86 gm and 183 gm impact of 96.5 mm ID cylinder, where R is centerline radius. Impact energy = 0.213 J.

Fig 5. Comparison of hoop strain profiles in 2.86 gm and 183 gm impact of 96.5 mm ID cylinder. Strain computed at inner surface for x/R and $\theta=0$ with respect to impact site, where R is centerline radius. Impact energy = 0.213 J.